

Bellinge dataset

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Open data set

- Made during an industrial PhD-study with a utility company VCS Denmark and DTU.

Paper

<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-4779-2021>

Dataset

<https://doi.org/10.11583/DTU.c.5029124>

Abstract. This paper describes a comprehensive and unique open-access data set for research within hydrological and hydraulic modelling of urban drainage systems. The data come from a mainly combined urban drainage system covering a 1.7 km² area in the town of Bellinge, a suburb of the city of Odense, Denmark. The data set consists of up to 10 years of observations (2010–2020) from 13 level meters, 1 flow meter, 1 position sensor and 4 power sensors in the system, along with rainfall data from three rain gauges and two weather radars (X- and C-band), and meteorological data from a nearby weather station. The system characteristics of the urban drainage system (information about manholes, pipes, etc.) can be found in the data set along with characteristics of the surface area (contour lines, surface description, etc.). Two detailed hydrodynamic, distributed urban drainage models of the system are provided in the software systems MIKE URBAN and EPA Storm Water Management Model (SWMM). The two simulation models generally show similar responses, but systematic differences are present since the models have not been calibrated. With this data set we provide a useful case that will enable independent testing and replication of results from future scientific developments and innovation within urban hydrology and urban drainage systems research. The data set can be downloaded from <https://doi.org/10.11583/DTU.c.5029124> (Pedersen et al., 2021a).

Dataset

Up to 10 years of data

- 13 level meters
- 1 flow meter

SWMM and Mike Urban model
3 rain gauges and rain radar
CCTV etc.

Why?

- Research gap on real-life dataset
- End-users would be researchers, but also utility companies, or vendors.

Research	Utility company	End-users
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Start discussion of how to make experiments on real-life data• No need for explaining in detail the case area in other papers, as I have a paper to refer to.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Innovation. Does someone see something in our data that we dont?• Start discussion with other utilities on how best practice is in model building• Start discussion how to standardize data	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Access to dataset• Understanding of dataset• Understanding of work-processes• Many possibilities to work on different data• Cross-checking of results – as we have the same dataset• The aim was that the dataset is “stand-alone” and that end-users didn’t need interaction with authors.• Used as teaching material

Metadata

Folder	Subfolder	Data
#1 Asset data		Links.shp
		Manholes.shp
		Links_2007.shp
#2 Sensor data	2 Cleaned data	In-sewer sensors
	2 Raw data	In-sewer sensors
		Temperature at WRRF
#3a Rain gauge data		5425 - files CC BY-NC 4.0 \$
		5427 - files CC BY-NC 4.0 \$
		Aabakken - files
#3b Radar data etc.	3b DMI Meteorological station	DMI Meteorological station
	3b DMI C-band	DMI C-band
	3b Local X-band	Local X-band
#4 Drawings	4 Drawings	Drawings
	4 Photos	Photos
#5 CCTV		CCTV
#6 Orthophoto, DTM etc.	6 Digital Height model	DHM Height Curves
	6 Digital Height model (rain)	DHM Rain
	6 Background map 25	DTKmap25
	6 Background map 100	DTKmap100
	6 Geographical information	GeoDanmark
	6 Orthophoto	GeoDanmark orthophoto
#7 Models	7 SWMM	SWMM
	7 Mike Urban	Mike Urban - files
		Mike Urban + - files
	7 Mike Urban anno 2009	Mike Urban anno 2009
		Mike Urban + - files
#8 Catchment description	8 Land usage	OV-2016_NF-2013_v8.tif
	8 Catchment areas + imp.	Samlet_feb2019a_Bellinge.shp
#9 Scripts		Scripts

Access:

- Normally private data
- Third-party open access data
- Normally third-party subscription data

CC BY-NC 4.0
License type. Data must not be used for commercial purposes.

Other data have no additional restriction other than appropriate credit (CC BY 4.0).

Ownership:

- SDFE
- VCS Denmark
- DMI
- Developed for this study

- #1 Asset data and #3a Rain gauge data is following predefined structure with metadata as described in document in dataset folder
- #2 Sensordata and #3b Radar data etc. – did not have a standard format and I made it with the most important details.
- Generally I have made pdfs with descriptions of data and sometimes with metadata included.

Figure 13. Overview of the items in the data repository folders and their subfolders, with an indication of the ownership of the specific data and how these data sources are normally accessed. The sensor and rain data in Fig. 7 can be found in the folders “#2 Sensor data”, “#3a Rain gauge data” and “#3b Radar data”.

Workflow

Structuring of data

What can the data set be used for? What is needed to do specific analysis (=Maximum output of the effort)

Which data do I have, and for which period. Is there anything missing? Is there any additional information that needs to be included in the data

Organising and fetching data

Description of data. Do I have some documents describing some of the data. Metadata is also given, where it is not provided.

Checking everything and ensuring that all permissions are clear.

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